

Geomechanical and Petrophysical characterization of Bajo Barreal Formation in GSJB

P.A. Vidal

Conicet (Golfo San Jorge), Chubut, Argentina.

D.G Manzanal, J.O Allard, & C.B Laskowsky

Universidad Nacional de la Patagonia San Juan Bosco, Chubut, Argentina.

ABSTRACT:

This study presents geomechanical and petrophysical characterization focused on analyzing outcrop analog samples of clastic reservoirs and mudstones equivalent to the caprock in the area of Cerro Colorado de Galveniz (Chubut) and Cerro Ballena (Santa Cruz), Argentina. The mean and median values of dry density measured in rocks of Cerro Ballena (CB) locality are, at least 0.5 g/cm^3 higher than the mean and median values found in rocks of Cerro Colorado de Galveniz (CG) locality, having the CB a more comprehensive range of values in contrast with the range of values for CG which are narrower. The Schmidt hammer index shows that CB locality have higher values than CG, with a difference of 12R approximately among the median and mean values of both localities. The permeability was measured with a handheld portable air-permeameter and the highest values were found in the channel lithofacies. A marked heterogeneity was seen in the permeability values depending on the direction of the measurement. It was carried out perpendicular and parallel to the stratification, being the parallel bearing which presented higher values. This study demonstrates the potential of testing with portable tools for rapid and non-destructive geomechanical and petrophysical characterization. The results contribute to the comprehensive understanding of outcrop analogs to improve subsurface interpretations associated with static and dynamic models.

1 INTRODUCTION

Geomechanical and Petrophysical characterization of stratigraphic units is a fundamental methodology for analyzing hydrocarbon-producing sedimentary basins. The Golfo San Jorge basin has accumulated more than 39,300 wells drilled since 1907 and more than 13,500 active producer wells. However, geomechanical studies are scarce, while petrophysical contributions mostly focus on subsurface data, and outcrop studies are practically nonexistent. This deficit limits the calibration of static and dynamic subsurface models and the decision-making related to the behavior of geomechanical units. In particular, Bajo Barreal Formation is the fundamental lithostratigraphic unit of the most important petroleum system in The Golfo San Jorge Basin. This unit contains the main levels of hydrocarbon reservoir sandstones, and also its superior sequences are the caprock of the system. The outcrops of the San Bernardo Fold Belt constitute a source of analogs for the oil system par excellence. Previous studies in this region focus on sedimentology and fluvial architecture parameters, the characterization of clays, and studies of geochemical petrography, without covering the geomechanical or petrophysical parameters. This study presents geomechanical and petrophysical characterization focused on analyzing outcrop analog samples of clastic reservoirs and mudstones equivalent to the caprock in the area of Cerro Colorado de Galveniz, Chubut, Argentina and Cerro Ballena, Santa Cruz, Argentina. Both of the selected areas are separated 150 km, with the aim to evaluate the variability among the parameters (Fig. 1).

Unconfined compressive strength (UCS) is one of the most directly obtainable geomechanical parameters to evaluate rock strength. Generally, the UCS of rocks can be determined by two different methods: 1) The direct methods carried out in the laboratory as Uniaxial Compressive tests, as suggested by the International Society of Rock Mechanics and American Standards for Testing Materials (ISRM, 1979; ASTM D7012, 2004). These types of methods are based on procedures under strict sample preparation conditions (ASTM D4543, 2019), are expensive, time-consuming, destructive, and certificated machines are necessary (ISRM, 1979; ASTM D4543-19). 2) indirect methods for estimating the UCS of rocks, these are widely used due to several advantages, such as no specimen preparation, the use of unsophisticated and easily-applied equipment, in addition to the fact that it is not always possible to obtain quality specimens for laboratory tests if the rocks are weak and/or intensely fractured/weathered. The Schmidt Hammer is the most widely used instrument for the indirect estimation of the UCS in rocks in the field and from which reliable values are obtained if it is done on blocks of homogeneous lithology due to the fact that it is portable, affordable and requires no sample preparation.

Permeability is crucial to understand the petrophysical properties of reservoirs and caprock, being typically considered a critical parameter for hydrocarbon production. Permeability is generally estimated from well log data in the hydrocarbon industry. The laboratory determinations are expensive, time-consuming, and limited in the number of measurements. Due to this, testing permeability in the field with portable equipment may be the most reliable method of obtaining representative permeability measurements.

The purpose of this study is to contribute with a set of reference values of the main hydrocarbon production unit of the Golfo San Jorge Basin. Stratigraphic sections for geomechanical and petrophysical tests were carried out in the field. A portable handheld air permeameter measured *in-situ* permeability, and the Rock Schmidt hammer measured the rebound values "R" (Type L and N). The field data was correlated with laboratory studies of the mechanical properties (UCS) from core plugs.

2 GEOLOGICAL SETTINGS

The Golfo San Jorge Basin (GSJB) is located in central Argentinian Patagonia (45°00' - 47°30'S latitude, and 63°30' - 72°00'W longitude) and corresponds to an intracratonic basin elongated in an east-west direction (Fig. 1). It is surrounded by the North Patagonian region in the north; the Deseado region in the south; the South Patagonian Andes in the west, and, in the east, the limit is defined by subsurface information under the South American Atlantic Margin. The Golfo San Jorge Basin is divided into five regions according to the current structural style (Fig. 1). The Western Flank and The San Bernardo Fold Belt are characterized by positive inversion characteristics, whereas the North Flank, the Basin Center and the South Flank are distinguished for having east-west normal faults.

The economic relevance of GSJB is due to the fact that it is one of the most important hydrocarbon producing areas in Argentina. GSJB has produced up to 1500 billion m³ of oil from mainly conventional reservoirs in channel fills of Bajo Barreal Formation and its subsurface equivalents. The Bajo Barreal Formation contains the main levels of hydrocarbon reservoir coarse-grained sandstones, and also its superior sequences are the caprock of the system.

Figure 1: Digital Elevation Model showing GSJB limits and different sectors of the basin, studied areas at the San Bernardo Fold Belt are marked with red stars and urban centers in yellow.

2.1 Stratigraphy

As shown in a simplified lithostratigraphic chart (Fig. 2) the sedimentary record of the GSJB ranges from Middle Jurassic (Bahía Laura Group) to Miocene (Santa Cruz Formation). The focus of this contribution is Bajo Barreal Formation. This Formation was deposited throughout the Upper Cretaceous in an endorheic basin over an area exceeding 150,000 km² with maximum thickness up to 1,300 m due to its wide distribution, the paleoenvironment changes across the basin being represented by sandstones, conglomerates, and thick intervals of mudstones, tuffaceous mudstones and thin intercalations of tuffs in lacustrine fan-deltas, volcanoclastic alluvial fans, meandering and braided rivers, and ephemeral rivers. The Bajo Barreal Formation is divided into two members (Lower Member and Upper Member) based on the floodplain composition and the scale of the sandbodies being the Lower Member characterized by channelized sandstones interbedded with fine-grained tuffaceous strata, whereas the Upper Member is composed of large-scale, isolated channel sandbodies surrounded by grey siltstones and siliciclastic mudstones.

Figure 2: Simplified Chronostratigraphic Chart of the Golfo San Jorge Basin. The rocks studied in this contribution are contained within the Bajo Barreal Formation (Upper Cretaceous) highlighted in sky blue. Modified from Paredes et al. (2020)

3 METHODOLOGY

Geomechanical and Petrophysical characterization was carried out on two stratigraphic sections build up in the studied locations using the Jacob Staff. A total of 180 m and 48m thick of Bajo Barreal Formation was measured in CB (Section A) and CG, respectively. Three lithofacies associations were defined: 1) Siliciclastic Channels (sandstones) 2) Floodplains (mudstones) 3) Tuffs paleosoils (volcaniclastic rocks).

The sampling was performed by taking rock blocks samples of approximately 0.03 m³ and positioning them in the sedimentary logs. In addition, Schmidt hammer rebound index and air permeability measurements were carried out with portable equipment. Dry density and Unconfined Compressive Strength tests were conducted in the laboratory.

3.1 Schmidt Hammer

The rock hardness was measured with Rock Schmidt N-type and L-type hammers, which consist of a spring-loaded piston that slides on a plunger that releases a constant potential energy of N=2.207 Nm and L=0.735 Nm against a metal anvil that is in contact with the rock surface. Once the plunger hits the rock surface, the rebound is measured on an arbitrary scale from 10R to 100R and is called the rebound index R. According to the ASTM D5873 (2014) standard, the mean values were obtained from 10 representative measurements on the specimen. A total of 660 impacts were made (66 average R values) on outcrops and on block samples in a laboratory environment.

3.2 Air Permeability (K_{air})

We have measured air-permeability values (K_{air}) using a last generation portable permeameter in sample blocks. Measurements were performed both in perpendicular and parallel direction to the sedimentary layering (S_0) using 180 seconds as maximum time for pressure decline. The median values were plotted in the sedimentary logs.

3.3 Dry Density (ρ_d)

Dry Density was calculated following the Method A (Water Displacement) according to ASTM D7263 (2009). Previously, paraffin density was calculated as 0.87 g/cm^3 . Dry density was calculated using the following formula:

$$\rho_d = \frac{Md}{\frac{(Mc - M_{sub})}{\rho_w} - \frac{(Mc - Mt)}{\rho_p}}$$

where: M_d = mass of dry specimen; M_c = mass of wax-coated specimen; M_{sub} = mass of submerged paraffin-coated specimen; ρ_p = density of paraffin; ρ_w = density of water at test temperature; ρ_d = dry density.

A total of $n=57$ samples were analyzed, and we used the average dry density of every block sample.

3.4 Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS)

For UCS values, core plugs were prepared according to ASTM D4543 (2001). A total of 9 core plugs of homogeneous rock with diameter of 32 mm and slenderness ratio $L/D = 2$ and tested following ASTM D7012 (2014). For block samples with more than 1 core plug, the UCS considered was the average between both tests. Then, the UCS values and the R index measured on every block were plotted in a X-Y graphic, an exponential function was obtained as a result of a simple regression analysis.

4 RESULTS/DISCUSSION

In the CB locality, regarding the mechanical resistance values, the highest values were found in the CBS3 sample (fine-grained sandstones well cemented) belonging to channel lithofacies with values of $R_N = 58$ and $R_L = 56$, while the lowest values were detected in the CBS2 sample (medium to coarse-grained sandstone poorly cemented) belonging to channel lithofacies with $R_N = 26,5$ and $R_L = 28$. With respect to dry densities, the maximum value was found in the CBS5 sample (Marker Bed) with a value of 2.28 g/cm^3 , while the lowest value was seen in the CBS1 sample (coarse-grained sandstone with conglomerate base) with a value of 1.98 g/cm^3 . The highest estimated UCS is that of the CBS3 sample (fine-grained sandstone) with a value of 25.5 MPa and the lowest is that of the CBS2 sample (medium to coarse-grained sandstone poorly cemented) with a value of 3.4 MPa. Regarding air permeability, the highest permeability was measured in the CBS1 sample (coarse-grained sandstone with conglomerate base) of the channel lithofacies with a median of 2000 mD for the measurements made perpendicular to S_0 and 3200 mD for the measurements made parallel to the S_0 , and the lowest value was measured in CBS4 sample with a median of 44 mD (parallel to S_0) and 3 mD (perpendicular to S_0) (Fig. 3).

In the CG location, in terms of mechanical resistance values, the highest values were found in the CGS2 sample (massive tuff) with values of $R_N= 47$ and $R_L= 45.5$, which responds to a tuffaceous bed associated to paleosoils lithofacies. On the other hand, the lowest values were found in the CGS3 sample (very friable coarse-grained sandstone with poorly cemented) belonging to the channel lithofacies with $R_N= 14$ and $R_L=15.5$, respectively. Regarding the dry densities, the maximum value was found in CGS7 sample (medium-grained greenish sandstone) belonging to the top of a channel with an average value of 1.9 g/cm^3 , while the lowest value of dry density was found in the sample CGS2 sample (massive tuff) with a value of 1.53 g/cm^3 . The highest estimated UCS corresponds to the CGS2 sample (massive tuff) with a value of 7.9 MPa and the lowest to the CGS3 sample belonging to a very friable whitish channel sandstone with very abundant tuffaceous matrix with a value of 1.5 MPa. Regarding air permeability, the highest was measured in the CGS5 sample (greenish sandstone with cross-stratification poorly cemented) with a median of 1100 mD for measurements made parallel to the foresets and 374 mD for measurements made perpendicular to them. The lowest value was measured in CGS2 sample (massive tuff) with a median of 45 mD (parallel to S_0) and 22 mD (perpendicular to S_0) (Fig. 3)

A trend of the Rock Strength and Dry Density of the rocks concerning the stratigraphic position is not observed, and nor is there a clear relationship between them. The Rock Strength and Dry Density appear to be controlled by the lithology and the burial story curve.

Figure 3: Stratigraphic sections with: rebound number, dry density, UCS and permeability logs. A) Cerro Ballena (CB) stratigraphic section and B) Cerro Colorado de Galveniz (CG) stratigraphic section.

In general terms, the mean and median values of dry density measured in rocks of CB locality are, at least 0.5 g/cm^3 higher the mean and median values found in rocks of Cerro Colorado de Galveniz locality (Fig. 4A), having the CB a more comprehensive range of values in contrast with de range of values for CG which are narrower. Related to Schmidt hammer rebound index, CB locality shows higher values than CG, with a difference of 12R approximately among the median and mean values of both localities (Fig. 4B).

Figure 4: Violin and boxplot graphics of Bajo Barreal Formation samples: A) Dry Density; B) Schmidt hammer rebound number.

In the stress-strain curves, we can observe that the samples belonging to tuffaceous beds of lithofacies paleosoils show a plastic behavior at the beginning of the test and then a brittle behavior until the specimen breaks (Figs. 5A, B). The curves belonging to the medium to coarse-grained sandstones (lithofacies of the channel) (Figs. 5C, D) show a brittle behavior from the beginning of the test until failure.

In the case of the sample CGS3U1 and CGS3U2 (very friable whitish channel sandstone with very abundant tuffaceous matrix), they show a small development of plastic behavior at the beginning of the test.

This variability in the behavior of the samples could be linked to the genesis of the deposit and their tuffaceous content, with tuffs having a plastic behavior: CGS2U1, CGS2U2, CBS4U1 (tuffaceous paleosoils) and to a lesser extent CGS3U1 and CGS3U2 measurements (sandstone with tuffaceous matrix). It is hypothesized that this behavior at the beginning of the test can be caused by the micro-crack closure and due to the nature of the pyroclasts exposed to stress. To corroborate this hypothesis, it is necessary to make thin sections of the samples previous to the compression and after the compression to evaluate for instance, pumice and shards collapse in the samples tested.

Regarding the values of UCS and R, as can be seen in the profiles, the rock strength is not linked to the stratigraphic position of the samples. In floodplain lithofacies was observed that tuffaceous content increases de rock strength values, having the greatest strength in the column and with the highest Young's moduli (Table 1). This behavior is not seen in channel lithofacies probably due to the poor cementation or alteration of the tuffaceous matrix by fluid circulation.

Figure 5: Strain-Stress curves of Bajo Barreal Formation samples. A) Tuffaceous paleosoils samples (Cerro Galveniz). B) Tuffaceous paleosoils samples (Cerro Ballena). C) Channel sandstones samples (Cerro Galveniz) CGS3 in the middle of the stratigraphic column and CGS7 in the top, both separated 15 m. D) Channel sandstones samples (Cerro Ballena) at the beginning of the stratigraphic column. E) All Channel sandstones samples. F) All tuffaceous paleosoils samples.

Table 1. Young modulus calculated in the analyzed samples.

Samples	Lithofacies	Grain Size	E (MPa)
CGS2U1	Tuffaceous Paleosoil		27
CGS2U2	Tuffaceous Paleosoil		11
CGS3U1	Channel Sandstone	coarse	2
CGS3U2	Channel Sandstone	coarse	2.8
CGS7U1	Channel Sandstone	medium to coarse	4.2
CGS7U2	Channel Sandstone	medium to coarse	3.5
CBS4U1	Tuffaceous Paleosoil		46.8
CBS1U1	Channel sandstone	coarse	5.3
CBS1U2	Channel sandstone	coarse	3.6

CB locality have higher values on dry density and R index, this spatial variability in the parameters correlates with the degree of exhumation and the sedimentary overload of each locality, the more exhumation and the less overload, the lower values.

A trend of the Rock Strength and Dry Density of the rocks concerning the stratigraphic position is not observed, and nor is there a clear relationship between them. The Rock Strength and Dry Density are being controlled by the lithology.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The quantitative analysis carried out shows that the CB outcrops present, on average, the highest R index and the highest dry densities, while for CG the R index and dry densities are the lowest of the two studied locations.

The preliminary results of this study show a general trend within the profiles allows us to infer that the highest R values are found in rocks with the highest tuffaceous content in the sandstone matrix and, in turn, have an impact on the permeability, conferring the lowest permeabilities of the entire column, that is, in general terms, tuffaceous content increases rock strength and decreases permeability in floodplain rocks. It is observed that the highest densities do not necessarily coincide with the highest uniaxial compressive strengths, in fact, the two rocks with the highest UCS have intermediate or low densities.

This study demonstrates the potential of testing with portable tools for rapid and non-destructive geomechanical and petrophysical characterization. The results contribute to the comprehensive understanding of outcrop analogs to improve subsurface interpretations obtained from conventional well-logs which control the static and dynamic models. In particular, the data obtained could contribute to the calibration of rock types defined from the combination of well profiles that evaluate mechanical resistance, permeability and tuffaceous content. Future characterizations will increase the UCS data and the outcrop measurements in the main fluvial deposits for the calibration of the trends recognized in this study.

6 REFERENCES

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